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“The Tragic Fate of Katerina”- A Study Based on Alexander Ostrovsky’s ‘The Thunder Storm’

Dr. Jimly.P¹

Abstract

Alexander Nikolaevich Ostrovsky was the Russian dramatist of the 19th century. Ostrovsky is generally considered as the greatest representative of the Russian realistic period. His works deals with the daily life and social customs of particular groups and classes. He was more dispassionate and less distorted in the treatment of his characters. His dramas are among the most widely read and frequently performed stage plays in Russia. Ostrovsky’s The Thunder Storm (1859) is a five-act tragedy which portrays a realistic picture of the Russian patriarchal life. The play is a social criticism, which is pointed particularly towards the Russian merchant class. It depicts the desperation of a young wife who takes a lover hoping he will change her existence but his failure to do so leads her to commit suicide. Katerina’s longing for freedom from the bondage of a loveless marriage and the ferocious mother-in-law symbolizes every woman’s longing for their own freedom from the patriarchal society.

Keywords: *Katerina, Tikhon, Kabanikha, wife, frustrated, family, marriage, torture, sin, patriarchy, society, suicide.*

Alexander Ostrovsky’s ‘The Thunder Storm’ may be said to be the story of a light-hearted women Katerina who find herself refugee in the hands of death. She killed herself in order to become free from the frustrated life in her husband’s house. It can be interpreted as an act of protest against injustice. Suicidal behavior is a major problem worldwide from early ages till now. But it has received little empirical

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attention. Family conflict, domestic violence, familial stress, social isolation are all causes of suicide. The psychological and emotional pain that reaches intolerable intensity may be the primary factor that leads a human to commit suicide.

We are living in the postmodern era where feminism is getting more popular, but still in our society we can find lots of women committing suicide in the name of dowry, physical torturing, mental torturing etc. Here, Ostrovsky's heroine Katerina drowned herself in the Volga in order to escape from the torture of the society. Katerina's husband Tikhon loved her but he was not able to express his affection for her because of his aggressive mother Kabanikha. Kabanikha was a tyrannical mother-in-law and she had crushed Katerina's life. Katerina felt somewhat a prison life in Tikhon's house. In her childhood days she lived free as a bird. Her mother loved her above everything else. She dressed her up like a doll and never pressed duties upon her. She did only what she wanted to do, but here in Tikhon's house her mother-in-law always gave her orders and forced her to do the duties and she even told her not to sit gazing out the window. Since Katerina had lived in a loving and peaceful atmosphere in her maiden days, life after marriage became boring to her. Her mother loved her very much and gave her entire freedom, but her mother-in-law was very rude and not at all showed any affection to her. She even didn't allowed Tikhon to love Katerina. Katerina longed for eternal love. She wished her husband to be more romantic, but Tikhon was entirely under the control of Kabanikha and without her permission he couldn't even talk to his wife.

Katerina wished to go for evening walks with Tikhon, but Kabanikha forbade them. Kabanikha always complained to Tikhon that he never gave orders to Katerina but used soft words and never shout at her and threaten her. In order to get rid of these problems Tikhon found himself a relief in drinking. Katerina was not able to bear this situation. She was a young woman who always wanted to live in a world of fantasy. We can observe her mind from her conversation with her sister-in-law Varvara.

Katerina: "Why don't people fly like birds? Sometimes I fancy I am a bird. When I stand on top of a hill I want so dreadfully to fly! I'd take a little run, spread out my arms and fly away. Shall I try it now?" (Ostrovsky 178)

Katerina loved Tikhon very much. When he was going to Moscow, she begged him to take her with him. When Kabanikha allowed them for a private talk Katerina told Tikhon throwing herself into his arms.” Don’t go away, Tisha! Don’t go, I beg you; I implore you, for the love of God.

Tikhon: I’ve got to go Katya. How can I not go, once mama’s sending me?

Katerina: Then take me with you, do; oh, do!

Tikhon: (freeing himself from her embrace) I can’t do that

Katerina: Don’t leave me. Tisha! Something terrible will happen! Something terrible!

Tikhon: It can’t be helped, everything is settled.” (195-196)

When Tikhon was leaving to Moscow; we can see Kabanikha instead of consoling Katerina abusing her. Kabanikha : “Hanging on his neck, you shameless hussy? It’s not with a lover you are parting! It is with your husband, your lord and master? Or perhaps you don’t know the rule? Bow to him! Bow to the ground.” (197)

We can infer from Kabanikha’s words that she is a mother-in-law of a patriarchal society who imposes restrictive social norms to her family, that is why she told Katerina to consider Tikhon as his Lord and master, but we can’t agree with those patriarchal norms. A wife is not a slave to her husband. They are having equal rights. They are life partners and self-respect is applicable to both of them.

As a wife and a daughter-in-law, Katerina was very obedient and loving. Though Kabanikha was very impudent Katerina never spoke a word against her and she always obeyed her orders. Katerina always longed someone to love her. In her childhood her mother always cared her and after her marriage she failed to get the real love which she yearned. She always needed Tikhon’s presence and also wanted him to adore her, but Tikhon was extremely different from her wish. He always gave importance to his mother’s words. Actually, he was afraid of Kabanikha. Tikhon was a person who had no identity of his own. He had no courage to take his own decisions. It was Tikhon’s behavior that leads Katerina to disaster.

It was love Katerina longed for. After Tikhon’s departure she became attached to Boris their neighbor, not just because he was pleasing to her, but being so different from everybody in the way he looked and the way he spoke. She was drawn to Boris by her need of

love, which had met with no response from her husband, and by her injured feelings as wife and woman, and by the deadly boredom of her life, and by her longing for freedom, space, and bondless liberty. Boris was not heroic; he was not worthy of Katerina. He was just one of the circumstances making her doom inevitable. Though she was attached to Boris she never hated her husband. Her love for Tikhon remained the same in her mind. When Varvara talked about Boris to her, Katerina said to her “don’t speak to me of him, I beg you, not a word! I do not wish to know him! I intend to love my husband. Tisha, Tisha darling, I wouldn’t exchange you for anybody in the world! I had no wish to think about this, but you brought it up.” (190)

From these words it is clear that Katerina was true to her husband and she loved him more than anything in the world. As a wife she always wished for Tikhon’s presence, that’s why she begged Tikhon to take her along with him to Moscow, but Tikhon never cared her feelings and he even distressed her feelings as a wife. Tikhon’s this behavior forced her to fall in love with Boris. Actually, Katerina never wished to fall in love with Boris, but her desperate mind forced her to do so. She felt very lonely. In her loneliness she thinks” it will be very quiet in the house now. If there were children. What a pity I have none of my own; atleast I could spend my time with playing with them. I do love to talk to children.” (199)

Form Katerina’s thought we can understand how much she missed her husband and her longing mind to become mother and thus spending time by playing with them, but fate was cruel to her. She didn’t have any children. If Tikhon had given her a chance to become a mother, she must not have felt this much loneliness. In the absence of Tikhon, she could atleast spend time with her children. When Tikhon left her alone, she felt her life in her husband’s house a sort of imprisonment. She felt that her life was in misery day by day, without seeing a ray of light and never hoping to. The longer she lived the worse it gets. It was her mother-in-law who crushed her. It was because of her Katerina hated that house; every walls were hateful.

When Katerina engaged in an immoral relationship with Boris in the absence of Tikhon, she knew that she was doing a sin. Though they enjoyed every night, the thought that she was doing a dreadful sin made her more worry than before. But she knowingly did it in

order to get a mental satisfaction which she had been longing since her marriage. She was terrified on thinking about the consequences when anybody came to know about her relationship with Boris.

Katerina was very sensitive, that's why at the very moment on Tikhon's unexpected arrival she became gruesome. Without having the courage to conceal it any more she revealed everything to Tikhon in Kabanikha's presence. If Katerina had not revealed her affair with Boris, Tikhon would never come to know about it and she could live with Tikhon till the end as usual, but Katerina's honesty forced her to reveal it. Her love towards her husband and lover was sincere, that's why she confessed her betrayal to Tikhon. The good-hearted Katerina didn't want to cheat her husband. So, we can't find fault with her, because she had done all this when life in that house became intolerable to her

At the end, not able to live in that house Katerina decided to set out of the house. While she was walking alone in search of Boris, she tells to herself. "Nowhere. Nowhere to be found. What could he be doing now, poor darling? Only to say good-bye to him, only that, and then...then I'm even ready to die. I've ruined myself and him too, brought dishonor on myself, eternal disgrace to him. There is nothing I want, nothing that pleases me, not even the light of day. But death doesn't come. I cry out for it, and it doesn't come. Perhaps I would find some joy in life I lived with him. I am already a lost soul. How I long for him! If I cannot see you, love, at least hear me from the distance! Sweet wind, carry to him my sorrow and my longing! Blessed saints, how I long for him! (Goes to the river-bank and cries out in a loud voice) My love! My love! My soul! How I love you! Oh, answer me! Answer me!" (243)

On hearing these words, we can infer that Katerina was in a traumatic situation. Nobody was there to console her. When she saw Boris, she begged him to take her with him to Siberia. We can find earlier she was begging her husband to take her with him to Moscow, but he went alone because he was afraid of his mother. Now here Boris left her because he was not able to violate his uncle's words. In both the cases as a wife and as a lover her feelings were injured. If her husband Tikhon had taken her to Moscow this disaster would not have happened to her. The insecurity which she felt forced her to compel in both the cases. In her childhood days her mother loved

and cared her very much, but she failed to bring up her as a bold woman. She always considered Katerina as a doll. This effected in a negative way when Katerina came to Tikhon's house after marriage. She was always nervous and failed to take her own decision.

After saying good-bye to Boris, we can see Katernia standing deep in thought. She thinks "where am I to go now? Home? No, to go home is to go into the grave, just the same. Ah, no; the grave is better I don't want to think of hoe I shall live. Go on living? No, no! That is too terrible! I have come to hate the people, and the house; its very walls are hateful! I will not go back! No, no, I will not go! What difference does it make whether death comes to me or I go to death? I cannot possibly go on living, but it's a sin, nobody will pray for me! Aye those who love me will pray for me. (Goes to the edge of the riverbank and calls out in a loud voice) My own love! My hearts joy! Farewell!" (*Disappears*). (246-247)

The unfulfilled dreams of happiness in marriage and the pernicious situation in her husband's house forced her to commit suicide. Though Boris left that place and Tikhon was ready to forgive, Katerina ended her life by throwing herself into the river Volga. Her morality conscious and self-guilty conscious made her to do this. Though Katerina was able to break a taboo, she was unable to live with the guilt. As a wife of a high-class family there is no other way in front of her, because she knew that the society will torture her. Her traumatic experience is one of the major causes of her suicide. Trauma studies explore the impact of trauma in literature and society by analyzing its psychological, rhetorical and cultural significance. In Sigmund Freud's *Beyond the Pleasure Principle* (1920) he argues that trauma is an unrepresentable event that fundamentally fragments the psyche. Emotional and psychological trauma results from an extremely stressful event that causes severe disability in daily functioning. The anguish and frustration from the traumatic event in Katerina's life led her to commit suicide.

The tragic fate of Katerina arises from the unconventional system of the patriarchal society. As a playwright Ostrovsky succeeded in portraying the problems of a woman in a high-class society through his heroine Katerina, but he failed to keep loyalty to Katerina as an individual, because he didn't allowed Katerina to walk out from her husband and to seek a life in which her values as a human being

can be realized. Instead, he killed the heroine by saying that she killed herself and had done a sweet revenge to her husband and family. Through Katerina's suicide, Ostrovsky is supporting the male dominated society. For this we can take evidence from the play. Katerina: "I've got sin in my mind. How I Have wept, how I have fought with myself? But there's no escaping this sin. No escaping it. It is a sin Varvara, a dreadful sin." (P.182 Alexander Ostrovsky) From the quotes we can conclude that Ostrovsky tried to portray Katerina as a sinner. Here Ostrovsky purposefully made his heroine Katerina to tell that she was sinned. So, through Katerina's suicide, knowingly or unknowingly the author is conveying a message that morality plays a key role in patriarchal society and a sinned woman have no right to live in the society. So, in this play, as a writer Ostrovsky had not showed any justice to Katerina.

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